

THE EFFECT OF SOCIAL MOBILITY ON THE PSYCHOLOGICAL
CHARACTERISTICS OF YOUTH

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Abstract. In this article, the essence of the psychological views of Eastern thinkers on social mobility and the social views of Western psychologists are presented.

Key words: social mobility, Person and social group, innovation, innovation, technology, complexity, system, innovative environment, innovative pedagogical activity.

The psychological views of Eastern thinkers on social mobility differ in essence from the social views of Western psychologists. For a person of the ancient East, social mobility consists of self-awareness, giving up material interests on the way to spiritual perfection, striving for ownership of the spirituality of giving rather than taking from the outside world [1].

For the Eastern man, indulgence in individualism has always been a factor of "destruction", and being part of a community has been a factor of "quietness" and "carelessness". The need to ensure collective harmony formed the structure of state systems in the East in ancient times. Also, in the East, geopolitical complexities, severe weather, water problems, cultivation of agricultural products only by means of irrigation, issues of water resources conservation and purposeful use caused the need to create and manage certain centralized office systems. This led to the emergence of strong traditions of statehood in Egypt, India, Mesopotamia, China and Mavarounnahr from the middle of the 3rd millennium BC [2].

In the social life of the East, the implementation of social mobility is unique. This uniqueness covers the following aspects:

The tendency to prioritize sedentary life;

Tendency to improve the position of the individual and social group horizontally rather than vertically;

Application of the implementation of the mobility process by the representatives of the class with the status of special social peoples, that is, dervishes, Qalandars, Sayyids, Eshans and Zahids;

It takes into account the factors of mobility, the implementation of Hajj and Umrah based on the rules of the Islamic religion, the development within the scope of the position and status, and the promotion of the status and status of the person.

Social mobility is related in many ways to the factor of religious belief. The problem of spiritual unification of people, ensuring their social cohesion was better to find its effectiveness in the environment of polytheism and fetishism. Zoroastrianism arose in such an environment based on monotheism.

As a result of following this teaching, the order of living based on the observance of "Good thoughts", "Good words", "Good deeds" took place in the spirituality of the peoples of the East. The founder of this doctrine was Zarathustra, the son of Purishasp from Spitama, who fearlessly spread his doctrine among the representatives of any class living in the society, proving the correctness of its purpose and purpose. According to Beruni, Zarathustra was born 258 years before Alexander the Macedonian arrived in Central Asia[3].

Avesta, which has a wide place in the teaching of Zoroastrianism, is an important and unique source for studying the socio-economic life, religious views, worldviews, customs, and spiritual culture of the peoples of Central Asia in the pre-Islamic period [4].

As can be seen from Zoroastrian teachings, the family has been considered sacred in the East since ancient times. It was strengthened and prevented from cracking. On the contrary, great importance is given to population growth. A girl

who does not go to the ground on purpose was put in a sack and beaten 50 times. An unmarried young man was also given 50 lashes and ordered to wear an iron belt around his waist. Leaving the family for a period of three days is allowed only through the kaywana of the neighborhood. Staying away from the family for a month or more is formalized by the order of the ruler or regional governor. Since the family is the only source of society, the family issue has always been the focus of Zoroastrianism.

Thus, social mobility within family and marriage is strictly regulated. We believe that this idea was the scientific basis for social views in philosophical, political and social sciences, and later for the theory of social mobility.

Abu Mansur al-Moturidi's role in the study of the history of public opinion in Mawarounnahr is incomparable. "Kitab at Tawheed", "Kitab al-Maqamat" and "Kitab raddul awamil lil adla wa lil kabi" [5], the founder of the Moturidia school, which is a major trend in Sunni Islam it is appropriate to approach them as a doctrine about processes and, in particular, about the individual, to evaluate them as an integrated scientific sociological concept that calls for ideological and religious unanimity, which is in accordance with the lifestyle and mentality of the people of Mavarounnahr. Al-Moturidi's views can be evaluated as a reasonable standard, human dignity, the first sociological definition of the position of a person in society. The fact that a person can change his social position in society through faith in Al-Moturidi's works can also be taken as a basis from the point of view of social mobility in modern sociology.

Al-Moturidi theoretically supports that the possibility of a person's voluntary choice of channels of social mobility in changing his social status should not be directed against the community, and that the state is responsible to the individual just as the individual is responsible to the state.

In our opinion, Al-Moturidi's social views include the study of public opinion and social mobility in the matter of faith as a channel of social mobility of religion. He widely advocated that people of faith in the society strengthen their

faith, enrich it scientifically, and develop it. Because it is precisely the question of faith that determines a person's place in society in many ways. In the Islamic world, the presence of several sects, orientations, creeds and currents, and the recognition of a person's religious position by the representatives of society was considered important.

The change in the social status of Muslims in society as a result of Al Moturudi's founding of the Moturud Creed and all the Muslims of the Hanafia Madhhab following this creed also indicates the manifestations of social mobility.

In Mawaroonah, the sociological understanding and study of nature and society was significantly expanded by the thinker Abu Nasr Farabi, known in the East as "Muallimi Sani" (the second teacher) and in the West as the Aristotle of the East. He further developed the scientific-theologically based theory of human will by Abu Mansur al-Moturidi.

According to Farobi, man is social by nature and can live as a community only in interdependence. Because any person needs the help of others in order to meet his simple daily needs, others have to establish similar relationships.

The need for life creates a sense of community in a person and creates interaction. Farobi writes in his book "The City of Virtuous People": "Each person, by nature, needs a lot of things in order to fulfill his needs and become perfect. However, he cannot provide himself with all the things he needs, and for this he needs a society of people, each of the people in the society supplies him with the necessary things»[6].

It is noteworthy that, according to Farobiy, when living in a community, people not only satisfy their material needs, but also reach the "highest point of perfection", in other words, in the process of living and working together, people gain spiritual strength, become perfect, and learn the methods of forming their material and spiritual values. improves.

In our opinion, Farobi in his works meant the collective action of society representatives to rise from the existing lower class to the higher class by "to the

highest point of perfection". It is precisely such movements that appear in modern sociology as collective social mobility.

After looking at Farobi's views on socio-political issues, we come to the conclusion that there are similarities and differences between Farobi's views and the views of previous thinkers, especially Greek scholars and their contemporaries. These views influenced the social views of a number of thinkers after him.

Abu Rayhan Beruni also made a great contribution to the development of the theory of social sciences. Beruni's encyclopedic book entitled "Memorials from ancient peoples" can be regarded as a classic ethnosociological work dedicated to the analysis and synthesis of the events of the past five thousand years of human history. In this book, the great thinker wrote about the researches on society and the methods he used during the writing of the work:

"During the writing of this work, I became convinced that it is impossible to obtain real information by quoting evidence from mental things, comparing with observed things. This is determined by following only the "People of the Book" and various religious leaders, people of various professions and beliefs who follow these (beliefs), always basing their concepts. Then it is known by comparing the words and beliefs they bring for proof»[7].

In conclusion, because sociology is a science that requires a high level of wisdom, the researches of our thinking ancestors on the direct study of society, their works enriched with concluding observations were created during the years of spiritual and mental maturity. For example, Amir Temur's "Tuzuklari Temur", Mirzo Ulughbek's "History of Four Nations", Alisher Navoi's "Majolis un-nafais", "Nasayim ul-Muhabbat" and "Mahbub ul-Qulub" are among them.

As a result of studying the issues of social mobility in the works of Eastern thinkers, the following can be stated: In the East, the observance of the principle of settlement and preservation of community, that is, the transition from a nomadic lifestyle to a settled one, is also a social process of social mobility;

observance of periodicity of social mobility;

the principle of manifestation of social mobility for political purposes; manifestation of religious features of social mobility. That is, the manifestation of the tendency to define one's social status by changing one's beliefs confirms the above-mentioned points.

The creative and noble ideas of Eastern thinkers on establishing a virtuous society and a just state had a strong impact on the development of Western socio-political and philosophical thought. Advanced scientists of the West enriched the knowledge and views of sociology in many ways by studying the heritage of Eastern thinkers, translating their works into European languages and developing society.

List of references

1. Бекмуродов М.Б. Замонавий бошқарув социологияси. – Ташкент: Ёшлар НУ. 2020. – Б.9.
2. Арипов М.К. Социальная утопия как течение общественно-философской мысли в Средней Азии. – Ташкент: 1989. – С.55.
3. Беруний. Танланган асарлар. 1-жилд. – Тошкент: Фан, 1968. – Б.207.
4. Асқар Маҳкам. Авесто. – Тошкент: Шарқ, 2001. – Б.72.
5. Маънавият юлдузлари: (Марказий Осиёлик машхур сиймолар, алломалар, адиблар). – Тошкент: А.Қодирий, 1999. – Б.77.
6. Форобий. Фозил одамлар шахри. – Тошкент: Янги аср авлоди, 2016. – Б.233.
7. Беруний. Избранные произведения, 1-том. – Ташкент: Фан, 1957. – С.11.